

Analysis and Sustainable Development of Offshore Structures

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Message from the Guest Editors

Dear Colleagues,

Over the last few years, enormous efforts have been made to improve the energy sector by enhancing sustainability. The application of sustainable design approaches, the selection of low-impact materials, waste recycling and reuse, among others, are all factors in the construction of offshore platforms. The examination of offshore platform sustainability performance, including the creation of quantification methodologies, indicators, and other metrics, has also been extensively researched around the world.

We welcome articles that examine the design and analysis of offshore structures, sustainable development, wind turbine design, oil and gas platform design, market reviews, literature reviews and research papers on the asset standpoint to be submitted to this special issue. We encourage research into the characteristics of different components of the oil and gas industry, from design, exploration and transfer, and related issues like oil spillage, oil recovery, carbon capture and geotechnical survey. The main goal of this special issue is to address the key challenges, thereby promoting research on offshore structures.

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Editor-in-Chief

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Message from the Editor-in-Chief

I encourage you to contribute a research or comprehensive review article for consideration for publication in *Sustainability*, an international Open Access journal which provides an advanced forum for research findings in areas related to sustainability and sustainable development. The journal publishes original research articles, reviews, conference proceedings (peer-reviewed full articles) and communications. I am confident you will find the journal contributes to enhancing understanding of sustainability and fostering initiatives and applications of sustainability-based measures and activities.

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